

Influence live streaming TikTok to purchase intention of skincare products in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

TikTok Live Streaming accommodates the needs of sellers to be able to communicate two-way between sellers and buyers. A new type of online business called live streaming allows users to watch and make purchases. The host is the person who sells the goods during the live-streaming event, and the live streaming platform is the location where the live-streaming takes place. The purpose of this study is to further understand the factors that determine customer purchase intention through tiktok live streaming using the IAM model. In previous research, several variables in the IAM model have a positive correlation with purchase intention. This study aims to see the impact of adding one variable, namely perceived persuasiveness within the framework of the IAM model on purchase intention. This research aims to see the impact of adding one variable, perceived persuasiveness in IAM model framework on purchase intention. This study using the quantitative method was employed using partial least square structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). The SmartPLS 4.0 software was applied to examine the proposed model.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Tiktok Live is one of the advantages of the phenomenon and viral features by the Tiktok app recently. On Tiktok Live, Tiktok users can live stream and interact directly with their audience. Viewers can comment, share virtual gifts, and participate in chats during live streaming. Tiktok Live is commonly used by users to share everyday moments, creative content, talents, and Q&A sessions while interacting with their fans in real-time. The Tiktok app with the quickest growth in the post-pandemic period that had the most downloads app worldwide in 2020 and 2021. Tiktok are well-liked by people of all ages, from kids to adults [1]. In the top five platforms Tiktok have ranked fourth. The rating is based on the total amount of time users have spent, which averages 13.8 hours per month [1]. Tiktok firstly concentrated on dancing entertainment and humor, but over time it shifted its attention to entertainment, even livestreaming surpassing Instagram, Twitter and Facebook in terms of viewers and subscribers [2], [3]. Livestreaming is quickly emerging as an indispensable tool, enabling real-time and interactive communication across a wide range of industries. It provides marketers and advertisers with a dynamic and engaging platform to connect with their target audience in real time. By utilizing the interactivity and immediacy of live streaming, marketers can create authentic and immersive brand experiences, by integrating product showcases, interactive Q&A sessions, influencer collaborations, and behind-the-scenes glimpses-all while transcending geographical boundaries [4]. Tiktok live streaming can be

defined as a powerful tool that can be used for various purposes. Providing clear information from live streaming will reflect targeted marketing and have an impact on consumers. Clear delivery information indicates that communication is two-way and live streaming with many viewers and consumers is a great way to connect with people to make friends, sell products, increase viewership, share content, and also build an audience for the intention of buying a product. The majority of women still find that skincare products are essential. For this reason, they invest wisely in the future of their skin, particularly in facial care [5]. Research [6] indicates that the use of skincare and sun protection products is on the rise. By 2027, the global market for cosmetic goods, which is currently estimated to be worth USD 380.2 billion, is predicted to expand by 5.3%. The rise in the quantity of imported cosmetics presents an opportunity for international skincare brands to expand in Indonesia. As TikTok grew in popularity, skincare companies started incorporating the social media platform into their skincare brand marketing strategies. As a result, there is now more competition than ever for TikTok marketing due to the following facts [7].

There have been several studies on the elements affecting the purchase intention. One of the studies [8], in on the impact of eWom on purchase intention on skincare product. We have seen that the phenomenon of live streaming is currently one of the interesting sales tools because Tiktok Live Streaming accommodates the needs of traders to be able to communicate two-way between sellers and buyers which is the main attraction, besides that the aspect of assessing merchant performance on the marketplace platform is the speed in responding to questions and requests. It seems that live streaming via social media is becoming increasingly popular [4]. However, it is not yet clear how it affects consumers' online purchase intentions for skincare products. To gain a better understanding of this, we have conducted research using the information acceptance model (IAM) model measurement method. According to the research conducted by [8], several variables in the IAM model have a positive correlation with purchase intention. One more variable, persuasive perception was added to the calculation framework of the IAM model.

We hope to see how these two variables impact the IAM model framework in terms of purchase intention. According to studies by [9], [10], persuasive arguments have a major effect on customer responses. In addition to evaluating the mediating function of consumers' causal attributions [11] investigated the indirect effects of persuasive messages on the perceived utility of messages and associated attitudes. Furthermore, persuasiveness plays a crucial role in influencing consumers' perceptions of the value and suitability of information, according to [12]. This research expands on the IAM modelling by incorporating new variables. To highlight research needs and the things the researcher wants to observe, new variables, models, or perspectives are added. In this study, perceived persuasiveness will be incorporated into the primary model, which will be based on previous explanations and include IAM variables like "information quality," "information credibility (IC)," "information usefulness," and "information adoption."

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. IAM

The core tenet of IAM is derived from the Elaboration Likelihood Model and the Technology Acceptance Model [13]. [14] state that the information adoption model, or IAM, is used to illustrate how people process information and how computer-based interactions may affect their intentions and behavior. In the study conducted by [15], the IAM was introduced. The model takes into account various consumer behavior factors, including "Needs of Information" and "Attitudes Toward Information," that are related to information consumption. According to the research findings, IAM is a highly adaptable and extensible model. Wang [16], claims that the [14] IAM model, which explains how people process persuasive information, has been widely applied in information systems and marketing research. This model has been used in a number of studies, including [17]–[20]. Along with adding perceived persuasiveness to the model, this study employs IAM variables such as "information quality," "(IC)," "information usefulness," and "information adoption" as the primary model.

2.2. Information quality (IQ)

Information quality, as defined by [21], is the precision, comprehensibility, clarity, and dependability of the data that is stored in a system. Information has the power to influence people both centrally and peripherally, according to [14]. The central strategy is focusing on the content of the message, which is dictated by the strength of the argument. When it comes to online purchases of personal healthcare or cosmetics, product sentiment greatly affects consumers' likelihood to purchase. The peripheral route involves using simple decision rules to assess the message, such as source credibility. According to [22], users' subjective assessments of whether information attributes satisfy their needs or the requirements of the system are reflected in the quality of the information. Filieri [23] discovered that the most important component in determining the diagnostic or usefulness of information is its quality. Zhu *et al.* [20] contend that the evaluation of a product's usefulness is influenced by the quality of the argument, which serves as a representation of product information.

According to [24], users find information useful if they believe it to be accurate, comprehensive, and current. In [15], [25], [26] are just a few of the earlier research that have shown a positive correlation between information quality and usefulness. In the case of the food delivery service application, [26] discovered that the usefulness and usability of the provided information are positively impacted by the quality of the information. These conversations suggest that, from the standpoint of social media purchasing, information quality is a major factor in determining the perceived utility and usability of information [27].

Therefore, it can be hypothesized that:

H1. The Information Quality positively of Skincare Products Influences to Information Usefulness

2.3. IC

This credibility is important because it influences how persuasive the information is perceived during the persuasion process [28] assert that a crucial element influencing the persuasiveness of information is its credibility. Additionally, it has been observed by [29] that data shared by extremely reliable sources is typically considered valuable and helpful. According to [14], source credibility is one way that informational influence can spread peripherally. This can serve as a quick appraisal to decide whether a message is beneficial or not. It is discovered that the first element in the persuasion process is IC, which positively affects the usefulness of the information [8]. Furthermore, users' decision-making process is thought to be significantly influenced by the credibility of the information source, and when the information was deemed useful, there was a significant positive relationship found between users' behavioral intention and source credibility [30], [31]. Consumer views of the utility of information are influenced by the credibility of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) [15]. According to the analysis, the author, content, and presentation of eWOM are what determine its credibility [32]. Therefore, it can be hypothesized that:

H2. The Information Credibility of Skincare Products Influences to Information Usefulness

2.4. Information usefulness (IU)

It is clear that the usefulness of information is closely tied to its quality and credibility, as well as how persuasively it is presented [33]. Information that is comprehensive, lucid, pertinent, comprehensible, and detailed as well as information that comes from a reliable source is more likely to be valued by consumers. This utility plays a crucial role in the decision-making process and is frequently the initial stage of embracing new knowledge. Usable information needs to be valuable, helpful, and instructive, as noted by [33]. Moreover, research by [15], [28], [34] has demonstrated that a significant predictor of the usefulness of information is the source's credibility. Viewers may express or share their positive feedback with the streamer and other viewers when they engage in a complementary positive experience, such as feeling satisfied and content after absorbing the compelling messages. According to earlier research [35], [36], persuasive messages have a significant influence on consumers' decision-making processes and the behaviors that follow. Customers who find a message convincing are inclined to think they are making sensible decisions about what to buy based on their overall assessment [9]. According to a number of studies [15], [17], [37], there is a significant correlation between perceived persuasiveness and purchase intention.

Therefore, it can be hypothesized that:

H3. Perceived Persuasiveness of Skin Care Product Influences to Information Usefulness

2.5. Information adoption (IA)

According to [38], information adoption refers to the process by which a receiver internalizes and accepts information from external sources, based on how it enhances their expertise and capacity for judgment. Information adoption is strongly influenced by information usefulness, according to prior research, especially when it comes to purchasing decisions [39]. Live streaming communication is often studied using the information adoption model to gain insight into how intentions are formed from received messages [40]. Kemp [41] argues that purchase intention arises as consumers evaluate brands and create preferences. When consumers incorporate information into their decision-making process, it can influence their deliberation and eventually result in their intention to make a purchase. According to [23], adoption behavior is significantly influenced by the usefulness of the information, which is demonstrated through information diagnostics. Subsequent research by [8] revealed a positive and significant relationship between information adoption and usefulness. Hussain *et al.* [42] Information usefulness is defined as people's belief that applying new knowledge will boost and improve their performance. According to [32], respondents thought eWOM (electronic word of mouth) information was helpful since it informed them about various products. Whether it was negative or positive, real people-generated eWOM was found to be more advantageous. Abu-Taieh *et al.* [43] used the IAM in a study and discovered evidence of the influence of usefulness and adoption. According to their research, the degree to which users thought the material on YouTube could help them with their studies or work was known as information usefulness.

Therefore, it can be hypothesized that:

H4. The Information Usefulness of Skincare Products Influences to Information Adoption

2.6. Perceived persuasiveness

Persuasion is the process by which people or organizations employ particular techniques to change the thoughts and behaviors of others through the dissemination of messages, leading to the acceptance of their opinions and the accomplishment of the intended goal [44]. According to [45], trust towards the host is characterized by an individual's willingness to be open to the opinions and actions of others. According to [46], consumers typically have a stronger foundation for their purchase decisions thanks to affiliation and trust transfer. Because friends are more likely to overlook mistakes and encourage a sense of community, customers' trust is positively correlated with a feeling of familiarity and closeness from members [45]. Through the connection of IAM and TRA, this research study seeks to predict that consumers who adopt eWOM information are more likely to have purchase intentions [15]. According to research, a major determinant of whether people accept and interact with new information is their perception of its usefulness [19], [47]. This is especially true of the abundance of eWOM information that people encounter on social media platforms [48]. Therefore, there is frequently a positive correlation between adoption rates and the utility of eWOM information. According to studies [13], [14], [49], eWOM adoption can be a highly reliable indicator of consumer purchase intention. In the end, when information is seen as helpful, people are more inclined to interact with it and act upon it. Adoption of eWOM information from social networking sites (SNS) can boost the probability that customers will make a purchase [15]. Viral messages that are extremely helpful on social media can reinforce consumers' intent to buy goods advertised on these platforms [12], [50]. Perceived network online influence (NOI) inaws another important factor that influences eWOM information. NOI has a significant impact on consumers' purchase intentions, and through eWOM adoption, the antecedents of eWOM information can mediate the consumer's purchase intention and increase it.

Therefore, it can be hypothesized that:

H5. The Information adoption of Skin Care Product Influence to Purchase Intention

2.7. Purchase intention

Purchase intentions refer to the willingness of consumers to purchase a particular product or service based on their subjective assessment and overall evaluation [51]. Buying something is a conscious choice made by the individual [52]. According to [53], purchase intentions are defined as a consumer's intention to buy a good or service at a particular time or place. They are regarded as an essential component of effective marketing because they are a significant predictor of consumer behavior [54], [55]. Consumer intentions, which in this study would refer to online purchase behavior through live streaming TikTok, are said by [56] to reflect the degree of a person's willingness to engage in a specific behavior. as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Based on its purpose, this research uses a quantitative method approach. The research strategy used is a survey strategy, where respondents are asked to fill out a questionnaire to provide quantitative data. Six variables of information quality, IC, information usefulness, adoption, persuasive perception, and purchase intention will be measured in this study.

3.1. Questionnaire design

In the study, the questionnaire was divided into seven sections. The first section contained filter questions for those who watch live streaming and purchase skincare products. The second section focused on the identity of the respondent, while the third section aimed to measure information quality using questions

developed by [19], [23], [57]. The fourth section aimed to measure information credibility, using questions developed by [23], [28], [58]. The fifth section aimed to measure information usefulness, using questions developed by [33]. The sixth section aimed to measure information adoption, using questions developed by [38]. Finally, the seventh section aimed to measure perceived persuasiveness, using questions developed by [17]. All the measures used a five-point Likert-type scale, ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). Table 1 is the identity of the respondents and Table 2 is the question table for filling out the questionnaire.

Table 1. Respondent's characteristic

Description	Percentage	
Gender	Male	41%
	Female	59%
Age	< 18 Age	0%
	18 - 15 Age	18%
	26 - 30 Age	37%
	31 - 35 Age	30%
	36 - 40 Age	8%
Education	> 41 Age	7%
	Senior High	18%
	Associate expert (D3)	18%
	Bachelor's degree (S1)	61%
Revenue	Magister (S2)	3%
	< 3.000.000	8%
Description	3.000.001 - 5.000.000	28%
	5.000.001 - 10.000.000	31%
Gender	10.000.001 - 15.000.000	20%
	> 15.000.000	13%

Table 2. Item list questionnaire

Laten Variable	Item code
Information quality [19], [23], [57]	IQ.1. The hosts in TikTok live streaming provide valuable information about IQ1 skincare products, explaining their attributes and benefits.
	IQ.2. In my opinion, the skincare product information provided by the host in TikTok live streaming is clear and easy to understand.
	IQ.3. I find the skincare product information shared by the host in TikTok live streaming to be very detailed, providing a thorough understanding of the products.
	IQ.4. I Find product information shared by the host in the TikTok live streaming is of high quality and presents the products in a professional and informative manner.
Information credibility [23], [28], [58]	IC.1. I find that the skincare product information shared on TikTok Live Streaming is convincing.
	IC.2. Personally, I believe that the skincare product information provided on TikTok Live Streaming is trustworthy.
	IC.3. In my opinion, the skincare product information presented on TikTok Live Streaming is true.
	IC.4. The information about skincare products shared on TikTok Live Streaming appears to be trustworthy.
Information usefulness [33]	IU.1. I find the skincare product information on TikTok Live Streaming to be useful.
	IU.2. The skincare product information shared on TikTok Live Streaming is informative in my opinion.
	IU.3. For me, the information on skincare products provided on TikTok Live Streaming is helpful in evaluating the products.
	IU.4. The information on skincare products shared on TikTok Live Streaming has been really helpful for me to gain more knowledge about these products.
Information adoption [38]	IA.1. Recently, I have been learning a lot of new things about skincare brands by watching live streams on TikTok.
	IA.2. TikTok Live streams have become my go-to source for information about skincare products.
	IA.3. I find myself agreeing with the skincare product recommendations provided by the TikTok Live stream hosts.
Perceived persuasiveness [17]	P.1. One of the things I appreciate about TikTok Live Stream hosts is that they are able to convey the advantages of skincare products in a short amount of time.
	P.2. Another great thing about the TikTok Live Stream hosts is that they explain skincare products very informatively.
	P.3. The TikTok Live Stream Hosts also provide detailed information about each skincare product, which helps to convince me that the product is worth trying.
	P.4. I have noticed that TikTok Live Stream hosts can be very convincing when they distribute discount coupons to consumers for the purchase of skincare products.
	PI.1. Skincare products have caught my attention, and I am considering buying them in the future.
Purchase intention [15], [39]	PI.2. I think the next time I need skincare products; I will rely on the information shared during TikTok Live Streaming by the host to make my decision.
	PI.3. The next time I need skincare products, I will most likely purchase the ones recommended by the host on TikTok Live Streaming.
	PI.4. I am highly inclined towards buying skincare products from TikTok Live Streamings.
	PI.5. I am planning to purchase skincare products that have been recommended on TikTok Live Streamings.

3.2. Data collection and analysis

The research sample used in this study were users of the Tiktok live streaming feature in Indonesia. To expand the sample, a non-probability sampling technique called snowball sampling is used, because it is difficult to identify respondents who use or watch Tiktok live streaming. Questionnaires were distributed to targeted respondents or samples with specific conditions to collect their responses. The questionnaire was translated into English from Indonesian, as this research was conducted in Indonesia. The questionnaire distribution was done through Google Forms via WhatsApp or other social media platforms, informing the respondent criteria to get better targeted respondents. The minimum sample size was determined using the sample to indicator ratio. Sample characteristics include Indonesian TikTok users who know or have found skin care products on tiktok live streaming, who like to look for skin care product references on tiktok live streaming, and who participate or act as an audience for skin care products on tiktok live streaming. The sampling frame used is Indonesian citizens. From these 24 indicators, a total sample size of 313 responses was obtained and considered eligible for further analysis. Therefore, a variance-based structural equation modeling technique called partial least square (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 4.0 software is used [59], [60] used to process and analyze the collected data.

4. DATA ANALYSIS & DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Measurement model

SmartPLS 4.0 software was used to evaluate the data to fulfill the requirements for measurement model evaluation and structural model evaluation. To evaluate the measurement model, several indicators are used such as factor loading (FL), average variance extracted (AVE), Cronbach Alpha (CA), composite reliability (CR), Fornell-larcker ratio which is a more accurate measurement when using SmartPLS 4.0 Based on research by [61], [62]. According to [63], One way to measure whether items representing the same variable are highly correlated is through convergent validity. The FL indicator is used to determine whether the items assigned to a variable meet convergent validity. A value of at least 0.5 for FL indicates that the variable has convergent validity, and for this research, the minimum limit is set at 0.6. AVE is another value used to determine whether the items that measure a variable converge or not, and it should be more than 0.5 to be considered convergent. CA and CR are common techniques used for testing reliability, and a minimum value of 0.6 is considered quite good reliability [64]. According to [62], [65], the correlation for Fornell-Larcker should be smaller than the root AVE. The variance inflation of all items (VIFs) resulting from a full collinearity test should be equal to 3.3 for the model to be free from bias, according to [66], but the PLS method requires no bias to data from a composite model population [67]. The following lists the outcomes of the measurement model evaluation. In light of Tables 2 and 3, The measurements for discriminant validity (Fornell-larcker indicates that the correlation is smaller than the root ave), convergent validity (FL is above 0.5 and AVE is above 0.5), and reliability tests (CA and CR above 0.6) show that the measurement model evaluation for validity and reliability is in a satisfactory state. Furthermore, the data is not skewed because the VIF value is less than 3.3.

Table 3. FL, AVE, CA, and CR Results

Latent Variable	Item Code	FL	VIF	CA	CR (rho_a)	CR (rho_c)	AVE
IQ [19], [23], [57]	IQ1	0.706	1.233	0.674	0.675	0.804	0.506
	IQ2	0.747	1.359				
	IQ3	0.707	1.273				
	IQ4	0.684	1.240				
IC [23], [28], [58]	IC1	0.780	1.488	0.789	0.792	0.863	0.612
	IC2	0.782	1.573				
	IC3	0.763	1.558				
	IC4	0.803	1.648				
IU [33]	IU1	0.712	1.337	0.744	0.748	0.839	0.566
	IU2	0.783	1.476				
	IU3	0.751	1.456				
	IU4	0.761	1.395				
IA [38]	IA1	0.728	1.185	0.629	0.63	0.802	0.575
	IA2	0.757	1.260				
	IA3	0.788	1.302				
P [17]	P1	0.715	1.355	0.717	0.738	0.823	0.539
	P2	0.796	1.401				
	P3	0.775	1.422				
	P4	0.642	1.245				
PI [15], [39]	PI1	0.675	1.317	0.774	0.777	0.847	0.526
	PI2	0.724	1.401				
	PI3	0.709	1.424				
	PI4	0.779	1.575				
	PI5	0.733	1.513				

Notes: FL=Factor Loading; CA= Cronbach's alpha; CR = Composite reliability; AVE = Average variance extracted.

4.2. Structural model

The study's structural routes were assessed using the bootstrapping method. Five thousand subsamples were examined to evaluate the hypothesis. Figure 2 presents the R-square values of the model and the P-values of all the pathways because of the bootstrapping procedure. As observed in Figure 2 and Table 4, all hypotheses presented were supported, and the confidence interval values of the structural model did not cross the confidence interval, indicating that the results were significant. Regarding the first hypothesis, the study found a positive and significant influence of information quality on information usefulness ($\beta = 0.140$. T-values = 2.270). This finding aligns with previous research that has shown that information quality has a positive effect on information usefulness. The theory of [23] supports this result, which suggests that high-quality information criteria help consumers assess the quality and performance of a product. Therefore, it can be concluded that the information on product skincare presented on Live streaming TikTok possesses the characteristics of information quality to its recipients or viewers.

Table 4. Discriminant validity-fornell-larcker criterion

	Information quality	Information adoption	Information credibility	Information usefulness	Perceived persuasiveness	Purchase intention
Information quality	0.711					
Information adoption	0.455	0.758				
Information credibility	0.568	0.502	0.782			
Information usefulness	0.438	0.588	0.487	0.752		
Perceived persuasiveness	0.427	0.582	0.442	0.546	0.734	
Purchase intention	0.488	0.537	0.460	0.511	0.596	0.725

Notes: The bold results are the values for discriminant validity.

It was discovered that information credibility has a significant, positive impact on information usefulness ($\beta = 0.240$. T-values = 3.739). This is in line with earlier research findings and is corroborated by [36] findings, which indicate that credibility may lessen perceived risk and uncertainty in decision-making. It is noteworthy that live streaming tiktok can convince others to try the promoted skin care products, considering the significance of source credibility in assessing online information. The third hypothesis indicates that perceived persuasiveness has a positive and significant influence on information usefulness ($\beta = 0.380$. T-values = 7.122). This finding is in line with [17] research, which suggests that persuasive messages can be helpful in providing clear reasoning to support statements, thereby encouraging people to accept recommendations related to skincare products on live streaming tiktok.

The fourth hypothesis suggests that information usefulness has a positive and significant influence on information adoption ($\beta = 0.588$. T-values = 12.788). This result is also consistent with the hypothesis put forth by [33], according to which adopting information begins with its usefulness. According to [32], the usefulness of information is determined by how much it adds to the provision of knowledge or information, but [68] clarify that review helpfulness shows how much it aids in the evaluation of products by consumers. As a result, the information about skincare products on live streaming TikTok increases viewers' and recipients' familiarity with the products, boosting their acceptance and understanding. Regarding the fifth hypothesis, the study found a positive and significant relationship between information adoption and purchase intention ($\beta = 0.537$. T-values = 10.489). This is consistent with the theory of consumer attitude, which suggests that cognitive components such as knowledge, opinions, beliefs, and awareness influence conative components, such as the likelihood of taking a specific action or behaving in a certain way. The information provided by Live streaming tiktok has contributed to the knowledge of its recipients, who then accepted the information and recommendations. This has increased the likelihood of recipients gaining interest and having an intention to purchase the promoted skin care products.

As can be seen from the Q^2 values being larger than zero in Table 4, the study indicates that the exogenous factors have predictive implications for the endogenous variables. Based on the F^2 values, it was determined that the effect size of each predictor variable was modest for information quality, information credibility, perceived persuasiveness, and information adoption, and big for information usefulness. Additionally, [63] recommends utilizing R-squared to assess the accuracy of the model by calculating the percentage variation of the construct. The proposed model's ability to explain the variation in information usefulness, information adoption, and purchase intention of skincare products by live-streaming TikTok users is tested in this study using R-squared. Based on Table 5, the R-square of information usefulness is 0.386, meaning that 38.6% of information usefulness's variance is explained by information quality, information credibility, and perceived persuasiveness. The R-square of information adoption is 0.346, indicating that 34.6% of information adoption's variance is explained by information usefulness. The R-square for purchase intention

is 0.289, suggesting that 28.9% of purchase intention's variance is explained by information adoption. The R-squared value higher than 0.60 is considered preferable according to [69]. Garson [70] suggests that 0.67 indicates a strong correlation, 0.33 indicates a moderate correlation, and 0.19 indicates a weak correlation. Based on this classification, information usefulness and information adoption are considered moderate, while purchase intention has the weakest prediction power.

Figure 2. Path model result

Table 5. Evaluation of structural model results

Hypothesis	Relationship	β Value	T-Statistics	P-Values	Confidence Intervals		R ²	Q ²	F ²
					5%	95%			
H1	IQ -> IU	0.140	2.270	0.012*	0.040	0.245	0.140	0.020	
H2	IC -> IU	0.240	3.739	0.000*	0.133	0.343	0.386	0.240	0.059
H3	P -> IU	0.380	7.122	0.000*	0.471	0.471	0.380	0.179	
H4	IU -> IA	0.588	12.788	0.000*	0.512	0.665	0.346	0.588	0.529
H5	IA -> PI	0.537	10.489	0.000*	0.456	0.625	0.289	0.537	0.406

Notes: IQ=Information Quantity, P= Perceived Pesuasiveness, IC = Information Credibility. IU= Information Usefulness, IA = Information Adoption, PI = Purchase Intention. *Significant

5. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

In previous studies only examined the field of e-wom with its relationship to purchase intention. in this study we made a study of live streaming and its impact on purchase intention. The findings show that in Tiktok live streaming, the strong factors that influence skincare purchase intention in Indonesia are information usefulness and information adoption. These two are the most important resource for customers. The significance and importance of internet live streaming in the marketing area has drawn the attention of several scholars and marketers in recent years. To comprehend the impact of information adoption on consumers, the information adoption model has been consulted. It was demonstrated that all of the suggested theories were true. Three further factors, namely perceived persuasiveness, information quality, and information credibility, also have a less substantial impact on the utility of information. This suggests that further variables that affect users' intentions to purchase Tiktok live streaming should be looked at in subsequent studies. This aids advertisers in determining the subject matter of the article. These results will help to more effectively target the demands of consumers. Customers themselves may learn from and analyze the direct path from information usefulness to adoption by consulting their own customers as well as the customers of their rivals.

5.1. Implications

The study indicates that hosts can step in and reinforce the information conveyed by giving a brief explanation of the skincare products offered in the live stream. This makes the host's offers easier for viewers to comprehend and take advantage of. Gaining a deeper understanding of their clientele can help marketers control the content that hosts. Additionally, by researching and evaluating the opinions of the customers themselves regarding live streaming, recommendations based on the direct path of information usability of information adoption can be made. These results will help copywriters better target the needs of their target audience. It is possible to enhance management and marketing efforts by taking into account factors like information quality, credibility, and perceived persuasiveness.

5.2. Suggestions skincare brands

It is recommended that skincare brands concentrate on using live streaming TikTok as part of their marketing strategy based on the research findings and the hypothesis. TikTok live streaming works well for reaching target audiences, as evidenced by the adoption of information hypothesis on purchase intention. While

established skincare brands can use Live streaming TikTok for Business to create campaigns, new market players can introduce their brands to the large audiences on the platform. When live streaming on TikTok, it is critical to share information about the features of the product and make use of the hosts' and viewers' roles in disseminating information and boosting perceived persuasiveness. Selecting reputable hosts and beauty bloggers is advised to further boost the credibility of product information.

5.3. Limitations and future research directions

There are certain limitations to this study that should be noted. First off, because it exclusively looks at the beauty product sector and analyzes live streaming on TikTok as a social media platform, The findings may not be applicable across all social media platforms. Furthermore, because viewers typically watch live streaming videos for extended periods of time, it's possible that their behavior will change over time and affect the findings of this study. Although the hypothesis was supported by the information adoption and perceived persuasiveness model, future research could examine additional variables like product quality, brand equity, price, and marketing mix to gain a deeper understanding of skincare brands' purchase intentions on Live streaming tiktok.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Kemp, "Digital 2021: Indonesia." Datareportal, 2021.
- [2] X. Wang, C. Yu, and Y. Wei, "Social media peer communication and impacts on purchase intentions: A consumer socialization framework," *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 198–208, Nov. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.intmar.2011.11.004.
- [3] M. Haenlein, E. Anadol, T. Farnsworth, H. Hugo, J. Hunichen, and D. Welte, "Navigating the new era of influencer marketing: How to be successful on Instagram, TikTok, & Co," *California Management Review*, vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 5–25, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1177/0008125620958166.
- [4] C. Shalabi, "Livestreaming: What it is and how it benefits marketers and advertisers." E-Marketer, 2023.
- [5] H. Nurhayati-Wolff, "Cosmetics and personal care market in Indonesia - statistics & facts." Statista, 2023.
- [6] H. V. R. D. Nitesh, "Cosmetics market by category (skin and sun care products, hair care products, deodorants & fragrances, and makeup & color cosmetics), gender (men, women, and unisex), and distribution channel (hypermarkets/supermarkets, specialty stores, pharmacies, onlin." Allied Market Research, 2021.
- [7] L. Azizah, J. Gunawan, and P. Sinansari, "The influence of TikTok's social media marketing on brand awareness and interest in buying cosmetic products in Indonesia (Pengaruh pemasaran media sosial TikTok terhadap kesadaran merek dan minat beli produk kosmetik di Indonesia)," *Jurnal Teknik ITS*, vol. 10, no. 2, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.12962/j23373539.v10i2.73923.
- [8] Indrawati, P. C. Putri Yones, and S. Muthaiyah, "eWOM via the TikTok application and its influence on the purchase intention of something products," *Asia Pacific Management Review*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 174–184, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.apmr.2022.07.007.
- [9] A. Angst and A. Agarwal, "Adoption of electronic health records in the presence of privacy concerns: The elaboration likelihood model and individual persuasion," *MIS Quarterly*, vol. 33, no. 2, 2009, doi: 10.2307/20650295.
- [10] Bhattacharjee and Sanford, "Influence processes for information technology acceptance: An elaboration likelihood model," *MIS Quarterly*, vol. 30, no. 4, 2006, doi: 10.2307/25148755.
- [11] S. Sen and D. Lerman, "Why are you telling me this? An examination into negative consumer reviews on the Web," *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 76–94, Nov. 2007, doi: 10.1002/dir.20090.
- [12] D. D. Gunawan and K.-H. Huang, "Viral effects of social network and media on consumers' purchase intention," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 68, no. 11, pp. 2237–2241, Nov. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2015.06.004.
- [13] M. B. Davis, "Lags in vegetation response to greenhouse warming," *Clim Change*, 1989.
- [14] S. W. Sussman and W. S. Siegal, "Informational influence in organizations: An integrated approach to knowledge adoption," *Information Systems Research*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 47–65, Mar. 2003, doi: 10.1287/isre.14.1.47.14767.
- [15] I. Erkan and C. Evans, "The influence of eWOM in social media on consumers' purchase intentions: An extended approach to information adoption," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 61, pp. 47–55, Aug. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2016.03.003.
- [16] X. Wang, *Social media in industrial China*. UCL Press, 2016. doi: 10.14324/111.9781910634646.
- [17] K. Z. K. Zhang, S. J. Zhao, C. M. K. Cheung, and M. K. O. Lee, "Examining the influence of online reviews on consumers' decision-making: A heuristic-systematic model," *Decision Support Systems*, vol. 67, pp. 78–89, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.dss.2014.08.005.
- [18] S. Watts and G. Wyner, "Designing and theorizing the adoption of mobile technology-mediated ethical consumption tools," *Information Technology & People*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 257–280, Aug. 2011, doi: 10.1108/09593841111158374.
- [19] C. M. K. Cheung, M. K. O. Lee, and N. Rabjohn, "The impact of electronic word-of-mouth," *Internet Research*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 229–247, Jun. 2008, doi: 10.1108/10662240810883290.
- [20] D. H. Zhu, Y. P. Chang, and J. J. Luo, "Understanding the influence of C2C communication on purchase decision in online communities from a perspective of information adoption model," *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 8–16, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.tele.2015.06.001.
- [21] C.-C. Chen and Y.-C. Chang, "What drives purchase intention on Airbnb? Perspectives of consumer reviews, information quality, and media richness," *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 1512–1523, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.tele.2018.03.019.
- [22] G. Jiang, F. Liu, W. Liu, S. Liu, Y. Chen, and D. Xu, "Effects of information quality on information adoption on social media review platforms: moderating role of perceived risk," *Data Science and Management*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 13–22, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.dsm.2021.02.004.
- [23] R. Filieri, "What makes online reviews helpful? A diagnosticity-adoption framework to explain informational and normative influences in e-WOM," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 68, no. 6, pp. 1261–1270, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2014.11.006.
- [24] A. Alhemimah, "The influence of online reviews on saudi consumers' tourism destination choices," Doctoral dissertation, University of Plymouth.
- [25] A. Elwalda, I. Erkan, M. Rahman, and D. Zeren, "Understanding mobile users' information adoption behaviour: an extension of the information adoption model," *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 1789–1811, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1108/JEIM-04-2020-0129.

- [26] K. W. Leong, Y. Wang, M. Ni, W. Pan, S. Luo, and D. Y. C. Leung, "Rechargeable Zn-air batteries: Recent trends and future perspectives," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 154, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2021.111771.
- [27] M. A. Rahaman, H. M. K. Hassan, A. Al Asheq, and K. M. A. Islam, "The interplay between eWOM information and purchase intention on social media: Through the lens of IAM and TAM theory," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 17, no. 9, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0272926.
- [28] I. Erkan and C. Evans, "Social media or shopping websites? The influence of eWOM on consumers' online purchase intentions," *Journal of Marketing Communications*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 617–632, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1080/13527266.2016.1184706.
- [29] E. Ismagilova, L. Hughes, N. P. Rana, and Y. K. Dwivedi, "Security, privacy and risks within smart cities: Literature review and development of a smart city interaction framework," *Information Systems Frontiers*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 393–414, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10796-020-10044-1.
- [30] E. Abedi, D. Ghorbanzadeh, and A. Rahehagh, "Influence of eWOM information on consumers' behavioral intentions in mobile social networks," *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 84–109, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1108/JAMR-04-2019-0058.
- [31] T. X. Hui, "The effect of source credibility on consumers' purchase intention in Malaysia online community," *Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 12–20, 2017.
- [32] C. Ngarmwongnoi, J. S. Oliveira, M. AbedRabbo, and S. Mousavi, "The implications of eWOM adoption on the customer journey," *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 749–759, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1108/JCM-10-2019-3450.
- [33] S. Hussain, X. Song, and B. Niu, "Consumers' motivational involvement in eWOM for information adoption: The mediating role of organizational motives," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 10, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03055.
- [34] A. Haldar and N. Sethi, "Environmental effects of information and communication technology - exploring the roles of renewable energy, innovation, trade and financial development," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 153, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2021.111754.
- [35] J.-W. Kang and Y. Namkung, "The information quality and source credibility matter in customers' evaluation toward food O2O commerce," *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, vol. 78, pp. 189–198, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2018.10.011.
- [36] D. H. Tien, A. A. Amaya Rivas, and Y.-K. Liao, "Examining the influence of customer-to-customer electronic word-of-mouth on purchase intention in social networking sites," *Asia Pacific Management Review*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 238–249, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.apmr.2018.06.003.
- [37] C.-L. Chang, M. McAleer, and W.-K. Wong, "Risk and financial management of COVID-19 in business, economics and finance," *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, vol. 13, no. 5, May 2020, doi: 10.3390/jrfm13050102.
- [38] Xiao-Liang Shen, K. Z. K. Zhang, and S. J. Zhao, "Understanding information adoption in online review communities: The role of herd factors," in *2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, Jan. 2014, pp. 604–613. doi: 10.1109/HICSS.2014.81.
- [39] E. Ismagilova, Y. K. Dwivedi, E. Slade, and M. D. Williams, *Electronic word of mouth (eWOM) in the marketing context*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-52459-7.
- [40] A. Sardar, A. Manzoor, K. A. Shaikh, and L. Ali, "An empirical examination of the impact of ewom information on young consumers' online purchase intention: Mediating role of ewom information adoption," *SAGE Open*, vol. 11, no. 4, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1177/21582440211052547.
- [41] K. Kemp, "Top digital trends in 2023." Datareportal, 2023.
- [42] A. Hussain, S. M. Arif, and M. Aslam, "Emerging renewable and sustainable energy technologies: State of the art," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 71, pp. 12–28, May 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.12.033.
- [43] E. M. Abu-Taieh et al., "Continued intention to use of M-Banking in Jordan by integrating UTAUT, TPB, TAM and service quality with ML," *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, vol. 8, no. 3, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.3390/joitmc8030120.
- [44] C. Amos, L. Zhang, S. King, and A. Allred, "Aristotle's modes of persuasion and valence effects on online review trustworthiness and usefulness," *Journal of Marketing Communications*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 360–391, May 2022, doi: 10.1080/13527266.2021.1881806.
- [45] L. Liu, W. Chen, H. Zhang, Q. Wang, F. Guan, and Z. Yu, "Flexible and multifunctional silk textiles with biomimetic leaf-like mxene/silver nanowire nanostructures for electromagnetic interference shielding, humidity monitoring, and self-derived hydrophobicity," *Advanced Functional Materials*, vol. 29, no. 44, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1002/adfm.201905197.
- [46] S. Farivar, O. Turel, and Y. Yuan, "A trust-risk perspective on social commerce use: an examination of the biasing role of habit," *Internet Research*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 586–607, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1108/IntR-06-2016-0175.
- [47] J. E. Bailey and S. W. Pearson, "Development of a tool for measuring and analyzing computer user satisfaction," *Management Science*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 530–545, May 1983, doi: 10.1287/mnsc.29.5.530.
- [48] S.-C. Chu and Y. Kim, "Determinants of consumer engagement in electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) in social networking sites," *International Journal of Advertising*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 47–75, Jan. 2011, doi: 10.2501/IJA-30-1-047-075.
- [49] E.-S. Lee, T.-Y. Park, and B. Koo, "Identifying organizational identification as a basis for attitudes and behaviors: A meta-analytic review," *Psychological Bulletin*, vol. 141, no. 5, pp. 1049–1080, 2015, doi: 10.1037/bul0000012.
- [50] F. Madli, S. L. S. Jr, A. Totu, and S. N. S. Annuar, "Identifying the factors influencing information usefulness and information adoption in promoting organ donation through social media," *Journal of Media and Information Warfare*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 46–79, 2018.
- [51] W. B. Dodds, K. B. Monroe, and D. Grewal, "Effects of price, brand, and store information on buyers' product evaluations," *Journal of Marketing Research*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 307–319, Aug. 1991, doi: 10.1177/002224379102800305.
- [52] N. Spears and S. N. Singh, "Measuring attitude toward the brand and purchase intentions," *Journal of Current Issues & Research in Advertising*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 53–66, Sep. 2004, doi: 10.1080/10641734.2004.10505164.
- [53] S. Rahmi, R. Nadia, B. Hasibah, and W. Hidayat, "The relation between self-efficacy toward math with the math communication competence," *Infinity Journal*, vol. 6, no. 2, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.22460/infinity.v6i2.p177-182.
- [54] D.-H. Shin and F. Biocca, "Health experience model of personal informatics: The case of a quantified self," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 69, pp. 62–74, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2016.12.019.
- [55] N. Peña-García, I. Gil-Saura, A. Rodríguez-Orejuela, and J. R. Siqueira-Junior, "Purchase intention and purchase behavior online: A cross-cultural approach," *Heliyon*, vol. 6, no. 6, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04284.
- [56] I. Ajzen, "The theory of planned behavior," *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 179–211, Dec. 1991, doi: 10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T.
- [57] D.-H. Park, J. Lee, and I. Han, "The effect of on-line consumer reviews on consumer purchasing intention: The moderating role of involvement," *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 125–148, Jul. 2007, doi: 10.2753/JEC1086-4415110405.

- [58] W. Weitzl, *Measuring electronic word-of-mouth effectiveness*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2017. doi: 10.1007/978-3-658-15889-7.
- [59] C. M. Ringle and M. Sarstedt, "Gain more insight from your PLS-SEM results," *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, vol. 116, no. 9, pp. 1865–1886, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1108/IMDS-10-2015-0449.
- [60] M. A. Memon, R. T., J.-H. Cheah, H. Ting, F. Chuah, and T. H. Cham, "PLS-SEM statistical programs: A review," *Journal of Applied Structural Equation Modeling*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. i–xiv, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.47263/JASEM.5(1)06.
- [61] M. R. Ab Hamid, W. Sami, and M. H. Mohmad Sidek, "Discriminant validity assessment: Use of fornell & larcker criterion versus htmt criterion," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 890, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/890/1/012163.
- [62] J. Henseler, C. M. Ringle, and M. Sarstedt, "A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling," *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 115–135, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8.
- [63] P. D. Indrawati, *Management and business research methods convergence of communication and information technology (metode penelitian manajemen dan bisnis konvergensi teknologi komunikasi dan informasi)*. Bandung: PT Refika Aditama, 2015.
- [64] I. Ghazali, *Application of multivariate analysis with IBM SPSS 23 program (aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program IBM SPSS 23)*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro, 2016.
- [65] C. Fornell and D. F. Larcker, "Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error," *Journal of Marketing Research*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 39–50, Feb. 1981, doi: 10.2307/3151312.
- [66] N. Kock, "Common method bias in PLS-SEM," *International Journal of e-Collaboration*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1–10, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.4018/ijec.2015100101.
- [67] M. Sarstedt, J. F. Hair, C. M. Ringle, K. O. Thiele, and S. P. Gudergan, "Estimation issues with PLS and CBSEM: Where the bias lies!," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 69, no. 10, pp. 3998–4010, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.06.007.
- [68] J. Lee and I. B. Hong, "Consumer's electronic word-of-mouth adoption: The trust transfer perspective," *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 595–627, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1080/10864415.2019.1655207.
- [69] N. K. Malhotra and S. Dash, *Marketing research: An applied orientation*. Delhi: Pearson India Education, 2016.
- [70] G. D. Garson, *Partial least squares. Regression and structural equation models*. Statistical Publishing Associates, 2016.

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